

Synthesis of Didymocarpin-A

SWADHIN NATH, ANJAN BHATTACHARYYA[†]

and

P. K. SENGUPTA*

Department of Chemistry, University of Kalyani,

Kalyani-741 235

Manuscript received 14 July 1982, accepted 20 May 1983

THE structure of a new flavanone, didymocarpin-A, isolated from the leaves of *Didymocarpus peti-cellata* (Fam: Geaneriaceae) was previously established as I on the basis of spectral, chemical and synthetic evidence by Bhattacharyya *et al.*¹⁻³. The present communication deals with the total synthesis of didymocarpin-A (I).

2-Hydroxy-4,5,6-trimethoxyacetophenone⁴ (II) was condensed with benzaldehyde in alkaline medium to give 2'-hydroxy-4',5',6'-trimethoxy chalcone (III), which on cyclisation in presence of pyridine afforded 5,6,7-trimethoxyflavanone⁵ (IV). The latter on demethylation with anhydrous AlCl₃ in acetonitrile furnished 5-hydroxy-6,7-dimethoxyflavanone (V). Very recently, the flavanone (V) has been isolated from the whole plant *Onychium siliculosum*⁶. The latter flavanone (V) on persulphate oxidation yielded the desired flavanone, didymocarpin-A (I). The synthetic flavanone agreed well with natural didymocarpin-A and a direct comparison with the natural sample using tlc, m.m.p., superimposable ir, confirmed its identity.

I. R₁ = R₂ = OH
 IV. R₁ = OCH₃, R₂ = H
 V. R₁ = OH, R₂ = H

Experimental

2-Hydroxy-4,5,6-trimethoxyacetophenone (II): II was prepared following the method described by Rao *et al.*⁴.

2'-Hydroxy-4',5',6'-trimethoxychalcone (III): To a mixture of the above acetophenone derivative (II) (1.0 g in 70 ml alcohol) and benzaldehyde (2.0 g) aqueous KOH (6.0 g in 40 ml water) was added dropwise with stirring. The reaction mixture was

left for 3 days at room temperature and then poured into water and extracted with ether. The aqueous alkaline solution was acidified to give an orange-yellow solid, which was filtered and washed with 5% NaHCO₃ solution followed by water. It crystallised from alcohol to give (III) as orange-yellow plates, m.p. 105-7°, yield 0.8 g.

5,6,7-Tri-methoxyflavanone (IV): The above chalcone (III) (0.4 g) was refluxed with pyridine (10 ml) at 130-40° in an oil bath for 8 hr and left overnight at room temperature. The reaction product was cooled, diluted with water, acidified with HCl (1 N) and extracted with ether. After removal of the ether, the residue was chromatographed over silica gel (B.D.H., 60-100 mesh). Elution with petroleum ether (60-80°)-benzene (1:1) afforded a colourless solid which on crystallisation from benzene-petroleum ether furnished IV as colourless needles, m.p. 158-59°, yield 0.12 g.

5-Hydroxy-6,7,8-trimethoxyflavanone (V): To an ice cold solution of the flavanone (IV) (0.1 g) in dry acetonitrile (10 ml), anhydrous AlCl₃ (0.2 g) was added and refluxed for 1 hr. The solvent was distilled off and the residue treated with ice-HCl. The solid product was filtered, washed with water and crystallized from benzene-petroleum ether (60-80°) to yield V as very pale yellow needles, m.p. 150-2°, yield 0.08 g.

5,8-Di-hydroxy-6,7-dimethoxyflavanone (I): To a stirred solution of V (0.4 g) in a mixture of pyridine (5 ml) and aqueous KOH (0.3 g in 10 ml) was added potassium persulphate solution (0.5 g in 100 ml) during the course of 1 hr at 15-20°. The colour of the solution changes from olive green to brown. After keeping for 24 hr at room temperature, it was acidified to Congo-red. A pale brown solid separated out and filtered. The filtrate was treated with Na₂SO₃ (1.0 g) and conc. HCl (10 ml) and kept over water bath for 30 min. A yellowish brown solid separated out and extracted with ether and dried. On removal of the solvent, the residue was chromatographed over silica gel (B.D.H., 60-100 mesh). Elution with benzene-ethyl acetate (9:1) furnished golden yellow crystals which on recrystallization with chloroform-petroleum ether (60-80°) gave golden yellow needles, m.p. and m.m.p. 213-15°, yield 0.1 g.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Professor N. Adityachaudhury, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya, Kalyani, for providing a sample of didymocarpin-A.

References

1. A. BHATTACHARYYA, A. CHOWDHURY and N. ADITYACHAUDHURY, *Chem. & Ind. (London)*, 1979, 348.
2. A. BHATTACHARYYA, A. CHOWDHURY and N. ADITYACHAUDHURY, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1980, 19B, 428.
3. A. BHATTACHARYYA and N. ADITYACHAUDHURY, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1982, 21B, 58.

[†]Department of Agricultural Chemistry, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya, Kalyani-741 235.

4. V. D. N. BASTRY and T. R. SESHADRI, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1946, 23A, 262.
5. H. G. KRISHNAMURTY and T. R. SESHADRI, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1959, 18B, 151.
6. TIAN-SHUNG WU, CHENG-SHENG KUOH, SHIEN-TSUNG HO, KEI-SHIEU YANG and KONG-KO LEE, *Phytochemistry*, 1981, 20, 527.

Synthesis and Screening of Some 4(5)-Arylhydrazonomethylenyl-2(3H)-imidazolethiones

AKHTAR ALI and R. K. SAKSENA*

Department of Chemistry, D.A.V. College, Kanpur-208 001

Manuscript received 28 January 1982, revised 21 October 1982, accepted 20 May 1983

A number of compounds having imidazole nucleus substituted at positions 1, 2 and 5 possess good therapeutic effects¹⁻³. Recently, some 2-mercapto benzoyl imidazoles have been found to exhibit pronounced fungicidal and amoebicidal properties⁴⁻⁶. A large number of hydrazones⁷⁻⁹ have also shown significant amoebicidal activities. Considering the importance of imidazole moiety and hydrazone group, we have synthesised some 4(5)-arylhazonomethylenyl-2(3H)-imidazolethiones and evaluated them for amoebicidal and fungicidal properties *in vitro*.

Experimental

All the melting points were determined in open capillary and are uncorrected.

α -Phenylhydrazone- γ -aminopurvaldehyde hydrochloride (II): Ethyl- γ -phthalamido- α, β -dioxobuturate- α -phenylhydrazone¹⁰ (I) (11.2 g; 0.04 mole) was heated with 30% hydrochloric acid (150 ml) till a clear solution was obtained. On cooling, most of the phthalic acid separated, was filtered off and discarded. The filtrate was concentrated to the

half of the total volume on a water bath and chilled in ice. Precipitated phthalic acid was again filtered off. The filtrate was evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure. A highly hygroscopic hydrochloride of α -phenylhydrazone- γ -aminopurvaldehyde, m.p. 150°, was obtained. (Found: C, 50.38; H, 5.40. C₉H₁₂ON₃Cl requires C, 50.58; H, 5.62%).

In case of other compounds, the hydrochloride in solution was taken for the next reaction.

4(5)-Arylhazonomethylenyl-2(3H)-imidazolethione (III): α -Phenylhydrazone- γ -aminopurvaldehyde (II) (4.27 g; 0.02 mole) was dissolved in water (100 ml), potassium thiocyanate (1.94 g; 0.02 mole) dissolved in water (10 ml) was added and the mixture heated on a water bath for 2 hr and finally evaporated to dryness. The residue was dissolved in warm water (50 ml) and treated with a saturated solution of mercuric acetate till the formation of yellow precipitate was complete. The precipitate was suspended in water (50 ml) and made acidic with dilute HCl. H₂S gas was passed to precipitate mercury sulphide which was filtered off and the filtrate was treated with animal charcoal and evaporated to dryness to obtain the hydrochloride of 4(5)-arylhazonomethylenyl-2(3H)-imidazolethione as a yellow hygroscopic substance. The hydrochloride was dissolved in dry ethanol and neutralised with ethyl alcohol and potassium hydroxide mixture. Precipitated potassium chloride was filtered off and the filtrate evaporated to crystallisation.

Purity of the synthesised compounds was tested by tlc using 50% ethanol as eluent and silica gel as adsorbent on the glass plate with iodine as indicator, when only one spot was observed. These compounds can exist in azo or hydrazone form. Wiley and Jorboe¹¹ confirmed from ir and uv data that the hydrazone form is more stable. Relevant data regarding compounds (III) are given in Table 1.

Pharmacological screening:

Determination of amoebicidal activity¹²: All the synthesised compounds were tested for their amoebicidal activity.

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTICS AND AMOEBICIDAL ACTIVITY OF 4(5)-ARYLHAZONOMETHYLENYL-2(3H)-IMIDAZOLETHIONES

Compound No.	Molecular formula*	R	m.p. °C	Yield %	Amoebicidal activity at the minimum inhibitory concentration of	
					1000 μ g/ml	500 μ g/ml
IV	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₄ S	H	228	20	+	+
V	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₄ O ₂ S	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	248	28	-	±
VI	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	<i>p</i> -SO ₂ NH ₂	264	20	-	-
VII	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₄ O ₂ S	<i>o</i> -NO ₂	269	24	-	+
VIII	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₄ S	<i>p</i> -OH	245	28	-	-
IX	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₄ O ₂ S	<i>m</i> -NO ₂	290	35	+	+
X	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₄ SOCl	<i>p</i> -Cl	232	26	-	+
XI	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₄ SOCl	<i>m</i> -Cl	224	24	+	+
XII	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₄ SOCl	<i>o</i> -Cl	240	24.5	-	+
XIII	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₄ S	<i>p</i> -C ₂ H ₅	259	33	-	±

*Carbon and Hydrogen analysis was found satisfactory.

(-) = Negative culture, (+) = Positive culture, (±) = Living culture and dead amoebae.

* Author for correspondence.